

Development of competence and professional competence of a teacher in higher education

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages Department of Theory of English
Language and Literature

Sh.O.Mamayoqubova

Email: mamayoqubovashahlo@gmail.com

Tel: +998937261746

Abstract. The role of a teacher at the present stage is being transformed into a high mission of forming a professional personality, which is designed to instill in students a readiness to acquire knowledge and improve professional skills throughout their lives. According to the authors, the goal of pedagogical education is the continuous general and professional development of a university teacher in order to achieve high results in practical professional activities. In general, the professional competence of a university teacher is a synthesis of professionalism (scientific, special, methodological, psychological and pedagogical training a), creativity (creativity of relationships, optimal use of tools, techniques, teaching methods) and art (acting and public speaking).

Key words: professional competence, self-awareness, self-development plan, self-manifestation, self-correction, profession, stereotypes, professional competence of a university teacher.

Abstrakt. Hozirgi bosqichda o'qituvchining roli o'quvchilarning hayoti davomida bilim olish va kasbiy mahoratini oshirishga tayyor bo'lishga qaratilgan kasbiy shaxsni shakllantirishning yuksak missiyasiga aylantirilmoqda. Mualliflarning fikricha, pedagogik ta'limning maqsadi – amaliy kasbiy faoliyatda yuqori natijalarga erishish uchun universitet o'qituvchisining uzluksiz umumiy va kasbiy malakasini oshirishdir. Umuman olganda, universitet o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetensiyasi kasbiy mahorat (ilmiy, maxsus, uslubiy, psixologik-pedagogik tayyorgarlik a), ijodkorlik (munosabatlar ijodkorligi, vositalar, uslublar, o'qitish usullaridan optimal foydalanish) va san'at (aktyorlik va mahorat) sintezidir. ommaviy nutq).

Kalit so'zlar: kasbiy kompetentsiya, o'z-o'zini anglash, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish rejasi, o'zini namoyon qilish, o'z-o'zini tuzatish, kasb, stereotiplar, universitet o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetensiyasi.

If he makes a conscious effort to get better, every teacher can master the art of instruction. Practice is the foundation for the development of these abilities. However, not all experiences lead to the development of useful professional abilities. Such a source can only be labor, when viewed in the context of its nature, objectives, and technology of activity. The personal, professional, and technical competencies of a teacher are combined to form pedagogical skills. The formation of teachers' desires and aspirations related to the improvement of their activities is significantly influenced by the growth of their professional competence.

Setting goals, studying specific concepts and ideas, and examining current theories are all connected to this in the first place. Depending on the areas of focus and the pressing needs at hand, the teacher is able to address multiple issues at once. It is necessary to take into account the interests of the general public when selecting the methods and means to accomplish the desired result. In the course of the educational process, the teacher interacts with each participant (parents, non-governmental organization representatives), and it is on this foundation that self-development occurs the improvement of his professional competence as a reader. The requirements established by the state and society for the educational system, the internal operations of the educational institution, the country's ongoing educational reforms, contemporary standards for a teacher's knowledge, skills, and experience, as well as knowledge of cutting-edge technologies, all have an impact on the nature of a teacher's activities.

The modernization of the educational process and the learning environment encourages educators to use innovative approaches and search for answers to their questions, which promotes the development of the educator's professional skills and of personal interests in self-education and learning. As a result, the atmosphere that is created in the educational institution benefits from the teacher's creative and professional development. Making an innovative environment based on collaborative creativity that enables students to work together to solve significant problems is crucial for the development of teachers' professional competence.

The formation of individual professional qualities, which involve ongoing development and self-improvement, results from the dynamic process of learning and improving professional experience. You should put a lot of effort into cultivating relationships with coworkers and on the sharing of knowledge and experience in order to decide on the objective and the strategy for achieving it.

The effectiveness of the teachers' work is enhanced by this exchange. We can assume that one specific objective for achieving successful outcomes is the development of teachers' professional competence. Teachers who are capable of self-perception and self-expression work hard to produce positive outcomes in their classes, which helps students develop self-respect and self-government.

The teacher's need for authority, the corresponding "authorities," and the trainees' subordination can all serve as incentives for the growth of the teacher's professional competence. However, management should be seen as an influence over others in order to accomplish the objectives set, rather than as the acquisition of power. Therefore, management for a teacher first and foremost refers to the creation of mutual interference. The start of a conversation and the development of friendly relationships are the defining characteristics of professional competence. The development of a teacher's professional competence is influenced by a variety of outside factors that must be considered.

The teacher's living and working environment is one of these variables. The following are the phases of developing professional competence: (a) self-awareness and awareness of need; (b) self-development plan; and (c) self-manifestation, analysis, and self-correction. The most significant problems in life are resolved, methods of resolution are determined, and efficient ways of achieving objectives are discovered when a teacher plans their work. In this process, it's crucial in particular to coordinate the activities of the teaching staff [1]. In general, a university teacher's professional competence consists of a set of abilities for organizing scientific and practical knowledge for the best resolution of pedagogical and educational tasks.

A university teacher's professional competence is a synthesis of their professionalism (scientific, special, methodological, psychological, and pedagogical training), their creativity (creativity in relationships, optimal tool use, tricks, techniques, and teaching methods), and their art (acting and public speaking). Today, it is abundantly clear that it is impossible to "compose" a competent professional from a simple body of knowledge because a university instructor must also instill a strong sense of moral responsibility in today's students.

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